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THE BASIC DIRECTIONS OF THE PERFECTION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF STUDENTS AT PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES**ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА В ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ УНИВЕРСИТЕТАХ**

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Abstract. The issue of improving the basic training of students in pedagogical higher education institutions vocational educational institution is discussed in this article. The basic positions of continuing pedagogical education are presented. Qualities that make the future teacher competitive in the contemporary economic conditions and training system capable of ensuring their development is suitable is discussed. It is suggested that the education system is a reflection of the processes taking place in the organization of labour, and also clarifies that in the conditions of modern society and education, there has been a significant change in the requirements of the modern specialist for successful productive activity in the professional sphere. The vocational–pedagogical and pedagogical higher educational institutions of Russia are analyzed in terms of popularity and effectiveness. The directions of the improvement of the basic training of students in pedagogic and vocational pedagogical institutions are suggested.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается вопрос совершенствования базовой подготовки студентов в педагогических и профессионально–педагогических вузах. Определяются основные положения непрерывного педагогического образования. Выделяются качества, которые делают будущего педагога в современных экономических условиях конкурентным, а систему обучения, способную обеспечить их формирование, пригодной. Определяется, что система образования является отражением процессов, происходящих в организации труда, а также уточняется, что в условиях современного общества и образования, произошло существенное изменение требований, предъявляемых к современному специалисту для успешной продуктивной деятельности в профессиональной сфере. Рассмотрены профессионально–педагогические и педагогические высшие учебные заведения России и проанализированы с точки зрения популярности и эффективности. Предлагаются направления совершенствования базовой подготовки студентов в педагогических и профессионально–педагогических вузах.

Keywords: basic training, educational institution, vocational educational institution, the teaching profession, problem–model training.

Ключевые слова: базовая подготовка, педагогический вуз, профессионально–педагогический вуз, педагогическая специальность, проблемно–модельное обучение.

The development of students' ability to love their pupils with all their flaws, the wish of finding the contact with the people of different age, the aspiration to qualitative work and constant self–perfection are the features of education in Russian pedagogical and professional pedagogical universities. In addition, a proper educational specialist must be able to keep audience's attention and have an interesting personality. The basement of future pedagogical career begins to set in during the study at university. Education at university gives not only the opportunity of professional competence's rising, but also, the skills of self–diagnostics and correction of professional and personal qualities, orientation at educational area and acquirement of friendly and professional relations [5].

In the contexts of modern society, the significant change of demands, presenting to a modern specialist for the successful and productive activity at the professional sphere, was changed significantly. They should have a versatile knowledge, a high level of competence, should adapt for new situations quickly, orient in the modern professional area easily, solve professional problems correctly and with responsibility, fulfil their potential (knowledge, skills, experience, personal qualities, etc.), use up-to-date achievements of science and technology possess responsibility for the results of their activity. These qualities make a competitive, in modern economical context, prospective educational specialist and the educational system that is useful to provide these qualities.

The main goal of academic activity at pedagogical universities is the qualitative familiarization of the content of particular subjects. Student's activity is determined by the studying of phenomena and regular patterns of the subject area that is under studying (pedagogical science, psychology, teaching methods of different subjects). A student has to learn how to solve pedagogical tasks, analyse decisions (situations) and take information from conterminous areas of knowledge.

According to I. V. Bogomaz, this lets to teach student not only to solve pedagogical tasks, but also formulate the problem, depending on what is one's knowledge and what is need to be defined, analyse if the decision is possible and whether is the only one decision or not, etc.; and also go to another more broad task, in which there are more possibilities to get rational decision.

It is necessary to teach student not only to analyse, but also to synthesize, actively subordinate the decision to the intended effect [1, 2].

On the basement of modern concept of the continuous pedagogical education, it is possible to distinguish following provisions:

1. Primary fundamental pedagogical education (college, institute, university).
2. Adaptation period. In Russia it is accepted to name this period — tutorship, when young and not very experienced teacher is attached to the teacher with great teaching experience. In the UK, the first year work is called — tutoring, in the USA — mentoring.
3. Further training (short–term and long–term courses).
4. Professional development through self–education.

It should be noted that the practical training is prevalent in the United States and England, in Russia the theoretical training of future professionals is predominant in the universities. In Russia it focuses on the special training — as a percentage it is almost 2 times more than in Britain and the United States. At the same time, it spends two and a half times less on the psychological and

pedagogical subjects, and finally teaching practice given time is three times less. It is considered that a thorough, fundamental studying of all disciplines makes up for a lack of professional training [6].

For the modern society the content of learning cannot be viewed separately from the educational process. The content and the results is the process of changing the properties and qualities of the person. The path of knowledge is no less important than the result [4].

Referring to Ledneva V. S., Lerner I. Y., Skatkin M. N., Pokholkov J. P., ect., I. V. Bogomaz determines the content of training as the transfer of social experience. It means that training allows the student to get a [1]:

–the system of knowledge about the nature, society, thinking, techniques and methods of activity, the assimilation of which ensures the formation of basis of purposeful people’s activity;

–a system of common intellectual and practical skills, which are the basis plurality of concrete kinds of activity and that provide the ability of younger generation to culture preservation;

–the experience of creative activity, providing the capacity for further development of culture;

–the experience of emotional and volitional interpersonal relationships, which are the basis of formation of outlook.

So, on the basis of all existing researches in this area, we had defined that the following positions can run out like ways of improving the basic training of students in pedagogical high schools:

1. The creation of unified system of basic professionally directed training of students.

2. The integration of the education, the science and the manufacture. The relationship of the solidity and professional orientation of knowledge have to become the main component of this integration.

3. It is need to connect the training of students with the problem-modular methods that directed to skills formation carrying out training and search-analytical activities.

4. The expansion of training objectives, providing the integration of basic and applied knowledge, the elaboration of methods, forms and means of education and the conduct of trainings on the basis of the problem-modular method.

5. The modularity of studied basic educational disciplines.

6. The methodological support of general scientific, scientific and profiling disciplines should comply with interdisciplinary contacts.

7. The inseparable from the learning process, educational activities should be provided like the professional practice.

The modern requirements to the fundamental preparation of students can be provided by the use of fundamentally new training and organizational–management means and methods of the education that are implemented on the basis of the problem-modular method.

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